

(4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.29 (10H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.85 (3H, t, CH₃).

(Z)-4-Undecenol (4): The alcohol (3; 8.4 g, 0.05 mol) was shaken with H₂-gas under pressure in presence of Lindlar's catalyst and a few drops of quinoline in dry n-hexane. When one equivalent of H₂ was absorbed, the hexane extract was washed with water and dried. Subsequent column chromatography afforded (Z)-4-undecenol (4; 7.65 g, 90%) (Found: C, 77.59; H, 12.85. C₁₁H₂₂O requires: C, 77.64; H, 12.94%); ν_{\max} (neat) 3 500–3 300 (OH), 2 900, 1 650, 1 470 and 720 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic), 3.6 (3H, m, CH₂OH), 2.1–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.5–1.6 (10H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.9 (3H, t, CH₃).

(Z)-4-Undecenyl bromide (5): To the ice-cooled mixture of the alcohol (4; 2 g, 0.01 mol), pyridine (1 ml) and dry ether (100 ml) was added dropwise PBr₃ (0.56 ml, 0.005 mol) with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. A little amount of cold water was then added to it followed by saturated solution of NaHCO₃ till effervescence ceased. The ether extract was dried and evaporated to get 5 (2.19 g, 80%). The absence of ir band at 3 500–3 300 cm⁻¹ (OH) confirmed the formation of the bromide (5). It was used as such for next operation.

(Z)-7-Henicosene (1): A mixture of Mg metal (2.24 g, 0.01 mol) in dry THF (10 ml) was stirred under N₂-atm. The reaction was initiated by the addition of a little amount of 1,2-dibromoethane and then the bromide (5; 2.33 g, 0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added. The Grignard so prepared was brought to the temperature -10° and decyl bromide (2.21 g, 0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added dropwise. After 1 h stirring, catalytic amount of Li₂CuCl₄ was added and the temperature (-10°) maintained for further 3 h. The reaction mixture was then quenched with saturated solution of NH₄Cl and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried and evaporated. Subsequent column chromatography using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) as eluent yielded 1 (1.75 g, 60%) (Found: C, 85.67; H, 14.32. C₂₂H₄₄ requires: C, 85.71; H, 14.28%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2 900, 1 650, 1 470 and 725 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic), 2.1–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.4–1.6 (30H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.8–0.9 (6H, m, terminal 2 × CH₃).

(Z)-7-Tricosene (2): It was prepared according to the procedure described for 1 (Found: C, 85.61; H, 14.38. C₂₃H₄₆ requires: C, 85.71; H, 14.28%); ν_{\max} (neat) 2 950, 1 660, 1 470 and 720 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.5 (2H, m, olefinic), 2.0–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.3–1.6 (34H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.9 (6H, m, 2 × CH₃).

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Synthesis of some New (E)-1,2-Bis(alkylthio and alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes

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It is evident from literature that some studies have been made on the reaction¹⁻⁴ of aromatic thiols with benzoin. However no attempt has been made on the reactions between aliphatic thiols with benzoin. Aromatic thiols react with benzoin and gave *trans*-1,2-bis(arylthio)stilbenes¹⁻⁴ in poor yields. On the other hand, aliphatic thiols with benzoin gave (E)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1a-f) in fair to good yields. Compounds 1a-f on oxidation with 30% hydrogen peroxide yielded (E)-1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2a-f) (Scheme 1). The bis(organosulphonyl)ethylenes⁵⁻¹⁰ are well-known for their fungicidal activity. Since benzoin with aromatic thiols gives only *trans* isomers²⁻⁴, the compounds obtained in the present investigation should also possess *trans* (E)-configuration.

R = OH₂(CH₂)₂, (OH)₂OH, OH₂(CH₂)₃, (OH)₂OHCH₂, CH₂(OH)₂, and (OH)₂CH(OH)₂

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The uv spectra (EtOH) were recorded on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 684 spectrophotometer.

(E)-1,2-Bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1). (E)-1,2-Bis(n-propylthio)stilbene: To a solution of benzoin (5 g) in glacial acetic acid (65 ml), n-propanethiol was added and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas for 2.5 h. Powdered zinc chloride (10 g) was then added to it and hydrogen chloride was passed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was left in a refrigerator for one day. The resulting crystals were filtered, washed with cold ethanol followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and recrystallised from ethanol (4 g, 77%), m.p. 86° (Found: C, 73.08; H, 7.17. C₂₀H₂₄S₂ requires: C, 73.17; H, 7.32%).

NOTES

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF (*E*)-1,2-BIS(ALKYLTHIO AND ALKYL SULPHONYL)STILBENES*

R	Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %	Compd. no.	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
CH ₂ CH ₂ CH ₂	1a	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂	86	77	2a	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂ O ₄	242	62
(CH ₂) ₃ OH	1b	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂	169	64	2b	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ S ₂ O ₄	277	78
CH ₂ (OH) ₂	1c	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂	96	59	2c	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂ O ₄	237	70
(OH) ₂ CHCH ₂	1d	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂	86	54	2d	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ S ₂ O ₄	274	58
CH ₂ (OH) ₂	1e	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ S ₂	51	56	2e	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ S ₂ O ₄	220	75
(OH) ₂ CH(OH) ₂	1f	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ S ₂	110	50	2f	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ S ₂ O ₄	224	76

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C and H analyses.

Similarly, other compounds (1b–f) were prepared (Table 1).

(*E*)-1,2-Bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2). (*E*)-1,2-Bis(*n*-propylsulphonyl)stilbene: A mixture of (*E*)-1,2-bis(*n*-propylthio)stilbene (656 mg, 2 mmol) in acetic acid (50 ml) and 30% H₂O₂ (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and cooled. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.54 g, 70%), m.p. 242° (Found: C, 61.36; H, 6.34. C₂₀H₂₄S₂O₄ requires: C, 61.22; H, 6.12%); λ_{max} 243 (ε 13 420), 226 (19 530) and 230 nm (20 810); ν_{max} 1 144 (SO₂), 1 220 (C–S) and 1 325 cm⁻¹ (SO₂).

Similarly, other bis-sulphones (2b–f) were prepared (Table 1).

The yields of (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes were fairly good. This may be attributed to the higher nucleophilicity of aliphatic thiols as compared to aromatic thiols.

The (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1a–f) exhibited a conjugation band around 305–310 nm region (ε_{max} 6 180–7 977). This band seems to be due to the conjugation of the sulphide groups with stilbene nucleus. In (*E*)-1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2a–f), the conjugation band occurred around 243–245 nm (ε_{max} 13 420–14 650). The hypsochromic and hypochromic shifts of conjugation band observed in 1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes may be attributed to steric effects of SO₂-groups which prevent the molecule from assuming a planar configuration. Similar optical properties were observed in *trans*-1,2-dihalo-substituted-stilbenes¹⁰.

In the ir region, besides aromatic bands, no C=C stretching frequency was observed in both bis-sulphides and bis-sulphones. This may be attributed to the symmetry of the *trans*-(*E*) compounds. The ir spectra of bis-sulphones showed characteristic bands at 1 144 (SO₂), 1 220 (C–S) and 1 325 cm⁻¹ (SO₂).

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A New Facile Synthesis of Uridyl-yl-(5'-3')-adenosine

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PROTECTING groups have been used for the synthesis of complex organic molecules by masking the sensitive groups in the molecule. Usual concept of protecting groups has been used only as 'masking' of the functional groups. A large number of activatable protecting groups¹ have been used for the synthesis of different oligonucleotides.

Nucleotide analogues have been very useful in the study of molecular biology. Synthetic oligonucleotides are being used for studying the mechanism of enzymatic actions on DNA *in vitro*² and elucidation of the genetic code³. Recently, several segments of DNA and RNA possessing interesting biological activities have been chemically synthesised⁴. Several analogues of purine-pyrimidine bases, nucleosides and nucleotides have proved very good antibiotics, anticancer and antiviral agents⁵. The chemical synthesis of a dinucleotide involves the joining of a nucleotide unit with another nucleoside through a phosphodiester linkage. Phosphodiester⁶ and phosphotriester⁷ are two methods of choice used